

A CREATIVE APPROACH TO LEARNING BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article discusses the issues of organizing digital-based education in the higher education system, the problems of increasing the scientific potential of future specialists in education, the study of the organizational and methodological foundations of teaching natural sciences, including the Department of Atomic Physics of Physics and Mathematics, the introduction of electronic educational resources of distance and independent learning through the possibilities of information technology (IT), the technologization of the educational process is devoted to the description of scientific research, aimed at achieving the set goals. It recommends electronic textbooks on physical processes, remote open online courses, optimal solutions for the use of educational tools in the training of future physics specialists.

Keywords: digital technologies, innovative methods, physical processes, education, electronic textbooks, remote open online courses, training, atomic, information technologies, modular.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы организации обучения на основе цифровых технологий в системе высшего образования, проблемы повышения научного потенциала будущих специалистов в образовании, исследование организационно-методических основ преподавания естественных наук, в том числе кафедры атомной физики физмата, внедрение электронно-образовательных ресурсов дистанционного и самостоятельного обучения через возможности информационных технологий (ИТ), технологизация образовательного процесса посвящается описанию научных исследований, направленных на достижение поставленных целей. В нем рекомендованы электронные учебники по физическим процессам, дистанционные открытые онлайн-

курсы, оптимальные решения по применению образовательных инструментов в обучении будущих специалистов-физиков.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, инновационные методы, физические процессы, образование, электронные учебники, дистанционные открытые онлайн-курсы, обучение, атомные, информационные технологии, модульные.

Introduction:

Improvement of the credit-module system in the system of training future specialists in the higher education system, the implementation of digital technologies in the educational process, and researches directed at IT-based modeling of complex effect phenomena are carried out in advanced scientific research centers and universities of the world, including: Universidad nacional de educación a distance UNED (Spain), Universidad de Valladolid UVA (Spain), Association for Educational Communications and Technology – AECT (USA), The University of Manchester UOMAN (England), Miyagi Pedagogical University (Japan), Politecnico di Milano POLIMI (Italy) , Fundacion Universidad Loyola Andalucía LOY (Spain), Belfield Pedagogical University (Germany), Center of Increasing Pedagogical Qualification on Base Manchester University (Great Britain), Sünne Hanna Eichler SE (Germany), Humance AG HUM (Germany) modern teaching theory and scientific research aimed at developing the methodology is being carried out. The scientific and research work on distance education carried out in developed foreign countries, including the US National University of Technology, the Open Universities of the Netherlands and Israel, the National Distance Learning University of Spain, the Shanghai Teleuniversity of China, and the open universities of Britain and Australia It is necessary to emphasize.

Analysis of literature on the topic

As a result of studying the created literature, scientific-methodical developments and practical works, it became known that large-scale works are being carried out in the process of teaching science. Among the large-scale reforms being carried out throughout our country, the youth of our country, pedagogic staff and experts in all fields are returning to the prestigious higher education institutions of the world and exchanging skills. At the heart of all these works, the goal is to train mature, knowledgeable, pedagogical and scientific potential highly qualified personnel. Therefore, we need to increase the potential of the teaching methodology of the "Atomic Physics" department, depending on the weight

of competitive personnel, introducing new educational technologies and various means of information transmission. We have briefly analyzed the literature, scientific researches and studies created in this regard.

Research methodology

Information technology in education is a set of forms, methods, methods and means of theoretically based educational process, which allow to achieve educational goals. In this, it relies on appropriate scientific modeling (designing), in the process of which these goals are given in the same sense and the possibility of objectively step-by-step measurement and assessment of the student's personal characteristics and qualities at a certain stage of his development is preserved. "Information technology" is a concept that interacts with scientific issues in any pedagogical system. However, if the scientific problem represents the goals of education and training, then information technology represents the ways of education and training and means of achieving them.

Analysis and results

It directly increases the importance and status of the student's independent work. If in the traditional education system, independent work is one-third of the complexity of the course, then in the credit system of education it is two-thirds. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the quality of independent education in the conditions of the credit system, which is becoming one of the main resources for training future specialists.

Today, the third version of independent work is being developed and is being processed in parallel. This type provides greater independence of students, greater individualization of tasks, the presence of consultation points and a number of psychological and pedagogical innovations regarding the content of tasks and the nature of consultation. All types of independent work fulfill their functions and are equally important for a future specialist.

In the special literature on pedagogy, there are descriptions of four independent works developed in accordance with the educational abilities of students:

1. Students copy assignments in the prescribed manner.
2. Reproductive activity to increase information about various characteristics of the studied object, mainly not going beyond memory.

3. Effective activity of independent use of received tasks to solve problems that go beyond the boundaries of a certain model, which requires the use of inductive and deductive methods.

4. Independent activity on transfer of knowledge in solving problems in completely new situations to create new decision-making programs, develop hypothesis-like thinking.

When organizing students' independent work, the following points should be taken into account.

- it is necessary to expand the use of independent work methods in educational practice;

- the criteria for using independent work methods should be the availability of educational material and students' readiness to use it at this stage;

- independent work methods should be used both in performing individual exercises and in the process of independent study of the material in performing exercises, tasks, answers to control questions, etc.;

- in order to bring the scope of independent work to an acceptable level, it is necessary to increase the preliminary preparation of students to perform it by forming the skills and qualifications of working with educational and informational materials, electronic resources on the Internet;

- it is necessary to use such methods of independent work that require students to show creativity, rationalization, innovation elements during the educational process;

- When using independent work methods, one should not forget about differentiated and individual approach. It is necessary to distinguish not only the complexity of the tasks, but also the measures of support provided by teachers in performing independent tasks.

Pedagogical literature also lists the conditions that ensure the successful completion of independent work:

1. Clear description of cognitive tasks.

2. Algorithm, method of doing work, student's knowledge of how to do it. The teacher clearly determines the forms of the report, the scope of work, and the deadlines for its submission.

3. Definitions of types of consulting support (consultations - installation, thematic, problematic).

4. Determination of evaluation criteria, report.

5. Determination of types and forms of control (seminar, tests, discussions, debates, etc.).

Successfully solving assignments helps the teacher to individualize training in this subject.

Based on all of the above, it is possible to distinguish goals such as individualization of education for any academic subject, in particular atomic physics:

1) development of individual characteristics of the student's personality and use in learning;

2) in the development and use of the knowledge interests of each student;

3) use in formation and development of intellectual abilities and talents of each student;

4) optimal development of reading ability for each student;

5) preparation for conscious choice of profession;

6) development of independent educational activity skills of each student. In this regard, the teacher of atomic physics should carefully study each student in terms of knowledge level, learning enthusiasm, interest and efficiency of abilities. To do this successfully, you can use a specific system of test exercises aimed at verifying:

1) level of study;

2) ability to work independently;

3) ability to understand the educational text and read quickly;

4) the ability to be intelligent;

5) level of development of one or another component of physical thinking;

6) cognitive interests, etc.

Two types of independent work are accepted in higher education: permanent and long-term.

Constant independent work every lesson

Conclusions and suggestions.

The method of organization of nuclear physics classes based on digital technologies in higher education institutions was analyzed, and the necessary suggestions and recommendations were made for improving its electronic-methodological support;

On the basis of the creation and implementation of teaching-methodical literature, such as "Physics" textbook, "Atomic Physics" Study

Guide" and coordination on the part of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. educational methodical supply of science has been improved.

The electronic textbook "Atomic Physics" was introduced into the educational process. This development is aimed at broadening the scientific worldview of students, understanding the achievements of modern science, intellectually understanding the theory of the structure of matter, and it served the in-depth study of the laws of "Atomic Physics" of future physicists and the development of their professional competence.

References:

1. Shavkat, Khaydarov, and Khuzhaniyozov Bakhrom. "ON THE IMPORTANCE OF ETHNOPEDAGOGICAL TRADITIONS IN THE UZBEK PEOPLE." Web of Teachers: Inderscience Research 2.5 (2024): 210-214.
2. Милиноров, Хусниддин Хушматович, and П. М. Жалолова. "ПРОЦЕСС ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ РАЗВИТИЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ В ВЫСШЕЙ ШКОЛЕ." Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies. Vol. 3. No. 5. 2024.
3. Хайдаров, Шавкат. "Роль этнопедагогики в узбекском народном традиции." Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi 7.4 (2024): 286-291.
4. Khaidarov, Sh. "MOTIVATION OF PEDAGOGICAL BACHELORATE GRADUATES FOR PROFESSIONAL TEACHING ACTIVITIES." Science and innovation 2.B12 (2023): 892-895.
5. Shavkat, Khaydarov, and Khuzhaniyozov Bakhrom. "ON THE IMPORTANCE OF ETHNOPEDAGOGICAL TRADITIONS IN THE UZBEK PEOPLE." Web of Teachers: Inderscience Research 2.5 (2024): 210-214.
6. Shamsiddin o'g'li, Haydarov Shavkat. "MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA INTERFAOL METODLARNI QO'LLASH USULLARI." Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi 23.1 (2024): 146-149.
7. Jalolova P.M. Atom fizikasi mashg'ulotlarini raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanib tashkil qilish metodikasi // Mug'allim hm yzliksiz bilimlendirio'. – Nkis, 2021. – №3/3. – B.121-125.
8. Asrorovna, Ochilova Gulnoza. "PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF THE JADID ENLIGHTENMENT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF GENDER CULTURE." (2023).
9. Ochilova, G. "JADIDS'PEDAGOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF GENDER CULTURE." Science and innovation 2.B12 (2023): 868-871.

10. Ochilova, Gulnoza. "DIDACTIC HERITAGE IN THE CREATION OF ABDULLA AVLONI." Академические исследования в современной науке 1.14 (2022): 121-123.
11. Ochilova, Gulnoza. "Areas of Study of Gender Relations in the Digital Economy." Архив научных исследований 4.1 (2022).
12. Jalolova P.M. Kredit-modul tizimida amaliy mashg'ulotlarni axborot texnologiyalari asosida tashkil qilish metodikasi // NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi. - Namangan, 2020. №5 - B.366-371
13. Милиноров, Хусниддин Хушматович, and П. М. Жалолова. "ПРОЦЕСС ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ РАЗВИТИЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ В ВЫСШЕЙ ШКОЛЕ." Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies. Vol. 3. No. 5. 2024.
14. Xusniddin, Milinorov, and Mavlonova Malika. "Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorlash jarayonida kommunikativ kompetentsiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi." Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi 7.4 (2024): 296-304.

